

CASE REPORT

Management of pulpal necrosis with acute apical abscess through simple exodontia: A case report

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Abstract

Odontogenic pain on a 48-year-old female patient with six implants in her dentition, swelling on the upper left quadrant of the jaw specifically her maxillary third molar (#28) which is a tooth away from the nearest implant were noted, her initial concern was her implant abutment. Percussion test and palpation test were done on maxillary third molar #28 and tested positive. Panoramic x-ray was taken as well and the results showed caries infection that compromised the periodontium. Root resorption was seen and extraction was the procedure the dentist opted and performed. Caries shown in the radiograph appeared to be present during her ongoing implant procedure but was possibly overlooked as the procedure was focused on the implant. Exodontia eased the tooth pain and removed the infected tooth.

Keywords tooth extraction, dental implant, dental caries, dental bone augmentation, mobile tooth

1 | Introduction

Chiefly, dental caries is considered a dietary-microbial condition. It is the chemical dissolution of a tooth surface brought on by metabolic activity in a microbial deposit covering a tooth surface at any specified time.⁵ Behavioral, psychological, and social factors also play a significant role in the disease process.⁶ The carious lesion

can also progress through the dentine to infect the pulp and periapical area.⁷ The pulpal tissue may eventually become necrosed, and the periapical inflammation may result in abscess formation.⁸ Caries on their own are painless but may become severe enough to result in the destruction that warrants tooth extraction as the final

consequence of most dentoalveolar diseases.⁹

Globally, exodontia is a routine procedure performed in dental practice.¹⁰ Studies have also shown that pain was the most prevalent self-reported reason for tooth extraction (37.5%), being the last resort primarily because of the lack of another treatment option.¹¹ The dental surgeon's experience, the time duration of surgery, the technique of anesthesia administration, and topical anesthesia are operative risk factors for exodontia.¹² This report aimed to present a case of management of pulpal necrosis with acute apical abscess through simple exodontia.

2 | Case presentation section

Figure 1. (A) Buccal view of a swelling gingiva of the upper left third molar. (B) Buccal view from the palatal aspect. (C) Mesial view from the palatal aspect.

2.1. Chief Complaint

A 48-year old female patient presented to the dental clinic with the chief complaint of pain and swelling on the upper left quadrant (Figure 1A-C). She described the pain as a dull pulsating type. The pain was intensified when pressure was applied such as when eating but was relieved when there was no occlusal contact on tooth #28. Patient was mainly concerned if the abutment of her implants done by a dental clinic in Manila, Philippines were directly involved.

2.2. Medical History

There were no significant medical findings in the patient's history.

2.3. Dental History

The patient had six tooth implants: upper right second premolar (#15), first premolar (#14), lateral incisor (#12), central incisor (#11); upper left second premolar (#25) and first molar (#26), done by a dental clinic in Manila last 2016 (Table 1).

2.4. Diagnosis

Intraoral examination revealed presence of localized pulpal necrosis with acute apical abscess surrounding the tooth. Tooth #28 tested positive for palpation test and percussion test. When air was introduced on the proximal areas of tooth #27 and #28, a foul ammonia smell was produced

Figure 2. (A) A dental panoramic radiograph showing implants on teeth #15, #14, #12, #11, #25, and #26. Removal dentures for the lower teeth. (B) A radiograph showing mesial caries on tooth #28.

which is an indication of long-standing caries. Panoramic x-ray was ordered (Figure 2-A). Big mesial caries was found on tooth #28 exposing the cervical third of the tooth (Figure 2-B). On her second appointment, panoramic x-ray showed a deeply involved caries on a periodontally compromised tooth (Figure 2-C). Fortunately, carious lesions did not progress and affected the adjacent abutment tooth supporting the bridge.

2.5. Prognosis

The extraction of the upper left third molar has a good prognosis. The overall prognosis of the case was favorable since there were no postoperative complications observed and the patient remained asymptomatic.

2.6. Treatment

With the patient's approval, she undertook the tooth extraction of tooth #28 and its follicular sac was

dissected under local anesthesia through infiltration technique. There were no incisions made, only elevation of the tooth with the use of 18L forceps. A prescription of 500 mg Mefenamic acid to be taken 1 capsule every 6 hours, 50 mg of Amoxicillin, 1 capsule for 3 times a day for 1 week, and 500 mg of Tranexamic acid to be taken when needed were given.

3 | Discussion

A patient's general apprehension towards a dental procedure is expected and should always be considered – no matter the treatment involved. In the researchers' case, the 48-year-old patient's diagnosis of pulpal necrosis with acute apical abscess was aggravated due to multiple factors. Most notably their psychological trauma after a long, tedious implant procedure. Another factor to note were the COVID-19 lockdowns, since the patient was

unable to travel from Butuan to Manila for follow-up appointments, where the implant procedure was performed. This prompted the patient to approach a trusted dentist in their hometown. First in 2016, when the temporary pontic was dislodged, and then in 2021, when the inflammation in their upper left quadrant was felt. Basic oral diagnosis guidelines dictate that any major procedure should always begin with a thorough clinical examination and ideally, an oral prophylaxis.¹ It is through these methods that the dentist will detect any developing problems that could hinder the major procedure.

The researchers can only assume that at some point, these were compromised, since the patient had their implant procedure done at a multi-specialty clinic involving multiple practitioners. This lack of a main overseeing dentist may have what brought out the complications that developed down the line, eventually forcing the patient to opt for extraction of Tooth #28. Dentist behaviors that are closely associated with patient satisfaction involve empathy and competency – putting the patient at ease while also assuring them of a successful procedure.⁹ These may have been fulfilled had it not been for the external factors that affected the procedure, as the patient had their implant procedure done in another city.

The psychological trauma that the patient experienced after the hours-long implant procedure was what eventually led them to decide on a removable partial denture on her lower teeth – instead of the implants that were initially considered. This procedure was done with the same dentist who eventually extracted Tooth #28. This particular case highlights the importance of a thorough oral diagnosis, early caries detection¹⁰, and a dedicated dentist that will oversee the entire procedure so as to produce a good prognosis. The patient was fortunate enough that the carious lesion did not progress and complicate the adjacent abutment tooth holding the bridge. A root canal was contraindicated for Tooth #28 due to the extent of damage, as well as accessibility concerns. The extraction procedure was successful and yielded a good prognosis.

4 | Conclusions

There are many preparations that must be made before having an implant tooth placed; an oral examination and an oral radiograph are required to determine if there are any cases that may disrupt the procedure; and the oral health must be in good condition before the procedure is performed. In this case, a small decay on the maxillary third molar was overlooked during the implant tooth procedure and worsened over time. The patient

complained of pain and swollen gums as a result, and an extraction was done to address and ease the pain.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist. All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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